

The Influence of Commitment, Work Participation, and Remuneration on the Performance of Local Government Agencies of Taliabu Island District

Sandra Jeanet Muntu¹, Aini Indrijawati², Mursalim Nohong³

^{1, 2, 3}Economic and Business Faculty, Hasanuddin University

ABSTRACT: This research aims to show the effect of commitment, work participation, remuneration on the Performance of Local Government Agencies in Taliabu Island District. The sample used is the local government in the Department, Agency, and SKPD Office of Taliabu Island District which includes heads, heads of fields, heads of sub-divisions, and employees. This study used a purposive sampling method. The type of data used in this research is primary data. Based on the distribution of questionnaires obtained a sample of 160 respondents. The results of the research show that commitment has a positive effect on the performance of local government agencies, while work participation and remuneration have no effect on the performance of local government agencies.

KEYWORDS: Commitment; Work Preparation; Reumeration; Local Government Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Changes that have occurred in several sectors, especially in the regional financial management system, have had a fairly good impact on the government, with efficient and effective services, budgeting of financial reports will be easier because of computerization, government performance reports will be more and more accountable because they have been published on the website. local government official. Regional government is essentially an instrument for implementing state development, so that state goals, especially those related to people's welfare, can be achieved easily. Designation of Government Issues by the Focal Government to independent locales in light of the Standards of Independence controlled in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 of 2014 concerning territorial government. With the presence of this regulation, it tends to be trusted that it will speed up the accomplishment of local area government assistance in further develop administrations, strengthening, local area cooperation and increment provincial seriousness by considering a vote based system, equity, obligation and the personality of a district. Independence makes changes in the public authority framework from centralization decentralization.

In the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 of 2014 concerning regional government it reads that Regional Autonomy is the right, authority and obligation of an autonomous region to regulate and manage its own Government Affairs and the interests of the local community within the system of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. The birth of regional autonomy creates the independence of a region in managing its financial resources so that it is able to compete and develop and build economic independence in accordance with the goals and objectives. The description of regional independence is reflected in regional autonomy, which is reflected in the ability of the region to manage its financial resources so that it is able to build quality economic independence to achieve the goals and objectives it aspires to.

With the presence of hierarchical responsibility, it gives serious areas of strength for an and assurance to be involved as an individual from a piece of the association. With the presence of HR who have a high obligation to the association, it will consequently impact working on the presentation of nearby government. Like that, hierarchical and individual responsibility have an extremely crucial connection to one another. Moreover with work cooperation in the readiness/arranging of the association's spending plan which is a main impetus for work inspiration so it can influence the degree of execution of government organizations. Spending plan is one of the significant variables in an association, with its position capability as making an interpretation of all methodologies into present moment and long haul plans. The budget planning tool consists of targets to be achieved by the organization. Bronwell, 1982 (in Husain 2014), states budget participation is a process of involving either individuals or groups who directly participate in it have an influence on the preparation and implementation, and their performance will be assessed from the achievement of the budget.

The reporting system is something that needs to be done to monitor the results of the work of the Local Government of Taliabu Island District so that the success rate of goals/achievements and deviations from the budget can be identified. So that it can be used as a benchmark in running the government system in the future. Therefore, this study aims to measure the effect of commitment, work participation, and remuneration on the Performance of Local Government Agencies in Taliabu Island District.

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HYPOTHESIS

Goal setting theory states that commitment and self-efficacy are the drivers of all behavior in organizations. Individual behavior is influenced by their individual understanding of organizational goals. Highly involved local government employees are usually eager to contribute to organizational goals. Responsibility is a person's inside inspiration to effectively uphold the progress of the association as per the objectives that have been set, so people focus on the interests of the association over the interests of people or gatherings. It is this individual motivation that leads to organizational success and ultimately strengthens the leadership capacity of local government institutions. Kurniawan's study (2013) suggests that commitment has a positive impact on the performance of local government agencies. It confirms the positive effect of commitment on leadership effectiveness. According to the expectation theory, strength depends on the expectations of each individual (Al Qadari et al., 2018). Individuals tend to maximize their actions when rewarded for what they want, for example rewards, incentives or rewards. With this, individuals always try to increase their individual effectiveness in achieving the given organizational goals. Until finally there is an increase in capacity. Based on the previous theory and research mentioned above, the following hypothesis can be formulated. Individuals tend to maximize their actions when rewarded for what they want, for example rewards, incentives or rewards. With this, individuals always try to increase their individual effectiveness in achieving the given organizational goals. Until finally there is an increase in capacity. Based on the previous theory and research mentioned above, the following hypothesis can be formulated. Individuals tend to maximize their actions when rewarded for what they want, for example rewards, incentives or rewards. With this, individuals always try to increase their individual effectiveness in achieving the given organizational goals. Until finally there is an increase in capacity. Based on the previous theory and research mentioned it, the following hypothesis can be formulated.

- H1: Commitment has a positive effect on the performance of local government agencies.
- H2: Work participation has a positive effect on the performance of local government agencies.
- H3: Remuneration has a positive effect on the performance of local government agencies.

Figure 1 Research Model

RESEARCH METHODS

This study was conducted at the Taliabu Island Regional Work Unit. The research subjects were government officials at the Department, Agency, and SKPD Office of Taliabu Island District which included heads, heads of fields, heads of subdivisions, and employees. The data used in this study is primary data obtained directly from the original source with quantitative data types. The research variable is in the form of a questionnaire containing certain statement items related to Commitment, Work Participation, Remuneration, and performance of local government agencies.

The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling with sample criteria namely SKPDs that carry out accounting or financial administration functions in SKPD Taliabu Island District and SKPDs it has aspects of convenience in reaching the information needed so that data collection is expected to be more effective and efficient. The data collection technique in this study used the survey method, namely by distributing questionnaires to respondents who worked in the Taliabu Island Regency Government. Respondents will choose the level of disagreement and agreement with the answers to the statements given. The metering scale used in this questionnaire uses a Likert scale model of 1 to 5.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Validity Test

No	Question	Factor Loading	Mark	Cronbach's Alpha
1	KI 1	0.703	0.936	0.985
2	KI 2	0.771		
3	KI 3	0.852		
4	KI 4	0.860		
5	KI 5	0.832		
6	KI 6	0.759		

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7	KO 1	0.811	0.747	Oh, 891
8	KO 2	0.553		
9	KO 3	0.607		
10	knockout 4	0.612		
11	KO 5	0.764		
12	Bible Study 1	0.839	0.653	0.772
13	par 2	0.844		
14	par 3	0.742		
15	par 4	0.714		
16	REM 1	0.820	0.680	0.898
17	REM 2	0.830		
18	REM 3	0.869		
19	REM 4	0.625		

Source: SPSS Outputs, v.26

In Table 1 it is shown the Commitment, Work Participation and Remuneration variables as well as the dependent variable Agency Performance have a value of 0.680, which value is greater than 0.5. Meanwhile, the factor loading for each question item is greater than 0.5, and it can be concluded that the question items for all variables are appropriate to use as a measuring tool.

Next, the table shows that the agency performance variable has a cronbach's alpha value of 0.985, the commitment variable is 0.891, the work participation variable has a cronbach's alpha value of 0.772, and the remuneration variable has a cronbach's alpha value of 0.898. The variables above have cronbach's alpha values above the significant level of 0.6. Thus it was concluded that the questions asked in the questionnaire which were broken down into the four variables used in this study had high reliability.

Table 2. Normality Test Results

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test	
asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.064

Source: SPSS output v. 26

In table 2 above it can be seen that the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) of 0.064 greater than alpha ($\alpha= 0.05$), meaning that the data is normally distributed. So, this research model is feasible to use.

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Results.

Variable	VIF
(X1)	1.303
(X2)	1,181
(X3)	1.196

Source: SPSS output v. 26

The multicollinearity test aims to test whether there is a correlation between the independent variables in the model on the basis of decision making if the VIF value > 10 , it is concluded that there is multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression, and vice versa. Based on Table 3 it is known that the Commitment, Work Participation and Remuneration variables have a VIF value <10 . It can be concluded that the regression model in this study does not experience symptoms of multicollinearity.

Table 4. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Unstandardized Residuals	
(X1)	0.723
(X2)	0.518
(X3)	0.875

Source: SPSS v.26 Outputs

Found on Table 4 above, it can be explained that Commitment variable has a significance value of $0.723 > (\alpha= 0.05)$, the work participation variable has a significance value of $0.518 > (\alpha= 0.05)$, and remuneration has a significance value of $0.875 > (\alpha= 0.05)$. Therefore it can be concluded that the regression model in this study is free from symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

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Table 5. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model	Regression Coefficient	std. Error	t	Sig.
Constant	17,062	3,934	2,098	0.000
Commitment (X1)	0.652	0.076	3,824	0.001
Work Participation (X2)	0.391	0.167	1,985	0.122
Remuneration (X3)	0.182	0.145	1,864	0.253
*) Significance at $\alpha = 5\%$		R² = 0.631		

Source: SPSS v.26 Outputs

According to the test results of the coefficient of determination in the table above, the Adjusted R Square (R^2) value is 0.631. This shows that 63.1% of Agency Performance variables can be explained by three independent variables, namely Commitment, Work Participation, and Remuneration. The remaining 36.9% is explained by other variables outside of the research model.

In the table of regression analysis results, the multiple linear regression model that can be formulated is as follows:

$$KI = 17.062 + 0.652KO + 0.391PAR + 0.182REM + e$$

Table 5 shows that the Commitment variable has a significance value of $0.001 < (\alpha = 0.05)$ with a regression coefficient of 0.652. This means that partially Commitment has a positive effect on the Performance of Local Government Agencies, with this so that the hypothesis is accepted. This can be interpreted that the higher the commitment an individual has in a government agency, the resulting performance will also increase. This is also in accordance with the theory of goal setting which states that commitment is the driving force of every organizational behavior. This research is suitable with the results of research by Sukmantari and Wirasedana (2015), and Kurniawan (2013) which state that commitment has a positive effect on the performance of an agency or managerial.

Furthermore, in table 5 it also shows that the work participation variable has a significance value of $0.122 > (\alpha = 0.05)$ with a regression coefficient of 0.391. That is, partially work participation is not influence the performance of local government agencies, so the hypothesis that is built is rejected. This result can be interpreted that the increasing participation in a government organization in this case SKPD Taliabu Island District then it still will not improve the performance of a local government agency. This also shows that human resources in SKPD do not meet good competency standards to support agency performance. The outcome of this study is not in line with research conducted by Wulandari and Riharjo (2016), Sukmantari and Wirasedana (2015), Triseptya et al., (2017), which state that work participation has a positive effect on managerial performance. However, the results of this study are in line with Yenti (2013) and Nazaruddin and Setyawan (2012) who state that work participation has no effect on managerial performance.

Table 5 also shows that the Remuneration variable has a significance value of $0.253 > (\alpha = 0.05)$ with a regression coefficient of 0.182. This means that partially remuneration has no effect on the performance of local government agencies, so the hypothesis is rejected. This can be interpreted that the greater the remuneration that individuals get will not improve the managerial performance of local governments. Even though compensation that is in line with workers' expectations increases motivation to work optimally. This is due to the lack of transparency and the uneven distribution of compensation received by workers, especially in SKPD Taliabu Island District. The results of this study do not support the expectation theory which states that this theory is about depending on the expectations of each individual. The results of this study are not in line with the research conducted by Kusuma and Ardana (2012), that remuneration has a positive effect on managerial performance. However, the outcome of this research is in line with Juniarti (2017) which claim that remuneration has no effect on agency performance.

CONCLUSION

This research aims to test and prove empirically about commitment, work participation, and remuneration on the performance of local government agencies (an empirical study on SKPD Pulau Taliabu). Based on the questionnaire distribution process, a sample of 160 respondents was obtained. The results of the study show that commitment has a positive effect on the performance of local government agencies, while work participation and remuneration have no effect on the performance of local government agencies.

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